

Legal Engineering of Aggression Against Our Culture: What is the State's Response?

From Registers to Innovative Tools: How Ukraine Can Break the Russian Algorithm of Cultural Property Appropriation

The Ministry of Culture of Ukraine has presented an algorithm of actions for tracing and returning cultural property. At the meeting of the interagency working group, the Office of the Prosecutor General, the Security Service of Ukraine (SSU), the Economic Security Bureau of Ukraine (ESBU), the National Police, the Foreign Intelligence Service, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and the Ministry of Justice were officially involved in the process.

This is a crucial step. The state demonstrates a transition from a reactive model to a systemic architecture of return.

The algorithm was presented by Deputy Minister Ivan Verbytskyi and Deputy Minister for Digital Development Anastasiia Bondar. The proposed model logically concentrates on what can be called the first-phase algorithm: creating an electronic Register of the Museum Fund of Ukraine, forming a list of stolen items, synchronizing with international databases, particularly Interpol, implementing European norms, and preparing an evidentiary base within criminal proceedings.

This is the foundation. Without accounting, documentation, and international registration of the crime, restitution is impossible.

But is this enough to break the Russian model of systemic appropriation of Ukrainian heritage?

The Russian Algorithm of Capturing/Destroying Our Culture: Not Chaos, but Legal Engineering

Russia rarely acts through spontaneous looting when it comes to museums. This is an operation with a legal cover.

International human rights reports, in particular the Human Rights Watch study on the events in Kherson, demonstrate a typical scheme:

1. Removal of legitimate management and appointment of a loyal "director".
2. Forging a request for supposed "evacuation for preservation".
3. Official decision by the occupation administration.
4. Extraction involving specialists from Russian museums.
5. Placing items on the balance sheets of Russian institutions as "temporarily accepted".

Thus, a war crime is masked as an administrative procedure, but all of this leaves a trace. The stolen property turns into an asset in the Russian accounting system and other databases.

Phase One: Register and Evidentiary Base

As of today, Ukraine:

- is preparing a fully-fledged electronic Register of the Museum Fund;

- is forming a public list of stolen items;
- submits notifications to the Interpol database (in particular regarding dozens of items from the Kherson Art Museum);
- implements Directive 2014/60/EU;
- ratified the Council of Europe Convention on Offences relating to Cultural Property;
- integrates data with international platforms.

This is a systemic preparation for international restitution processes. Effectively, the state is building a legal position for future litigation and compensation mechanisms.

Phase Two. From Registers to ARO/AMO: How to Break the Russian Algorithm of Theft

The Ministry of Culture presented an algorithm for tracing cultural property: creating registers, working with Interpol, and collecting evidence. This is an important foundation for recording the crime, but it is not enough to break the aggressor's strategy.

Russia does not act through chaotic looting. This is massive legal engineering: the occupiers simulate "evacuation," and Russian museums put the stolen exhibits on their balance sheets. A war crime is disguised as an administrative procedure in an attempt to legalize the proceeds of the crime. The stolen property becomes an asset in the Russian Federation, including a financial one, receiving budget funding, insurance, and grants.

Ukraine's response must be financial and institutional. The involvement of the ESBU in the interagency group opens the way to integrating restitution into the European Asset Recovery system (ARO/AMO networks) and using financial intelligence tools (AML/CFT).

We must treat the stolen heritage, among other things, as a property asset.

If a Russian institution uses our exhibit, its operations in the EU should be blocked through ARO/AMO mechanisms, and secondary sanctions should be initiated.

From Fixation to Impact

The first phase proves the fact of the crime.

The second phase makes the entire track of the crime transparent and leads to legal consequences.

If a Russian museum or other entity holding stolen exhibits risks losing access to international grants, insurance instruments, banking operations, or participation in international exhibitions, this creates a real price for the appropriation.

Conclusion

The algorithm presented by the leadership of the Ministry of Culture is an important stage in the institutional maturation of state policy in the field of returning cultural property. This is a strong first phase — accounting, recording, and international notification.

But a strategic victory will require a second phase — transitioning from registering losses to blocking and subsequently managing assets.

In modern warfare, culture is not just a symbol; it is property, evidence, and a financial resource — it is exactly what we are fighting for.

And the return will begin when every exhibit placed on the balance sheet of a Russian institution turns from an asset into a high risk.

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